

Introduction to NeutroNearrings

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Abstract. Algebraic concepts and structures are enriched with the special types of operations and axioms known as NeutroOperation and NeutroAxiom. Various types of NeutroAlgebras are studied using several such defined concepts. The objective of this paper is to introduce the concept of Neutro Nearrings. Several interesting results and examples of NeutroNearrings, NeutroSubRings, NeutroQuotientNearrings and NeutroNearring Homomorphisms are presented.

Keywords: Nearring; NeutroRings; NeutroNearring; Neutrosophy.

1. Introduction

The NeutroDefined and AntiDefined Laws, as well as the NeutroAxiom and AntiAxiom was first time introduced in 2019 by Smarandache [5, 6]. This concept has given birth to new fields of research called NeutroStructures and AntiStructures. For basic and recent results on Neutrosophy, NeutroAlgebraic structures and AntiAlgebraic structures we refer [5, 7, 8]. For basic and recent results on Nearrings we refer [3, 4].

In [2], Agboola formally presented the notion of NeutroGroups. In this he showed that in general, Lagrange's theorem and 1st isomorphism theorem of the classical groups do not hold

in the NeutroGroups. Also in [1], Agboola studied NeutroRing, Neutro subring, NeutroQuotientRings and he proved the 1st isomorphism theorem of the classical rings for this class of NeutroRing.

The present paper will be concerned with the introduction of NeutroNearings.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [8]

- (i) A classical operation is an operation well defined for all the set's elements while a Neutro Operation is an operation partially well defined, partially indeterminate, and partially outer defined on the given set. An AntiOperation is an operation that is outer defined for all the set's elements.
- (ii) A NeutroAlgebra is an algebra that has at least one Neutro Operation or one NeutroAxiom (axiom that is true for some elements, indeterminate for other elements, and false for other elements), and no AntiOperation or AntiAxiom. An AntiAlgebra is an algebra endowed with at least one AntiOperation or at least one AntiAxiom.

Definition 2.2. A Neutro group is a nonempty set G with binary operation $*$ satisfying following conditions:

- (i) $*$ is Neutro associative that is there exists atleast one triplet $(a, b, c) \in G$ such that

$$a * (b * c) = (a * b) * c$$

and there exists atleast one triplet $(x, y, z) \in G$ such that

$$x * (y * z) \neq (x * y) * z$$

- (ii) There exists a Neutro neutral element in G that is there exists atleast an element that is we have $e \in G$ such that

$$a * e = e * a = a$$

and for $b \in G$ there does not exist $e \in G$ such that

$$b * e = e * b = b$$

or there exists $e_1, e_2 \in G$ such that

$$b * e_1 = e_1 * b = b$$

or

$$e_2 = e_2 * b = b \text{ with } e_1 \neq e_2$$

(iii) There exists a Neutro inverse element that is there exists an element $a \in G$ that has an inverse $b \in G$ with respect to a unit element $e \in G$ that is

$$b * a = a * b = e$$

or there exists atleast one element $b \in G$ that has two or more inverses $c, d \in G$ with respect to some unit element $u \in G$ that is

$$b * c = c * b = u$$

$$b * d = d * b = u$$

In addition, if $*$ is neutro commutative that is there exists atleast a duplet $(a, b) \in G$ such that

$$a * b = b * a$$

and there exists atleast a duplet $(c, d) \in G$ such that

$$c * d \neq d * c$$

then $(G, *)$ is called a Neutro commutative group or Neutro abelian group.

If only condition 2.2 is satisfied, then $(G, *)$ is called a Neutro semigroup and if only condition 2.9 and 2.2 are satisfied, then $(G, *)$ is called a Neutro monoid [1].

Let R be a nonempty set and let $+, \cdot : R \times R \rightarrow R$ be binary operations of ordinary addition and multiplication on R . Then $'\cdot'$ is both left and right Neutro distributive over $'+'$ that is there exists atleast a triplet $(a, b, c) \in R$ and atleast a triplet $(d, e, f) \in R$ such that

$$a \cdot (b + c) = a \cdot b + a \cdot c$$

$$d \cdot (e + f) \neq d \cdot e + d \cdot f$$

then \cdot is left Neutro distributive over $+$ on a set R .

Suppose if there exists atleast a triplet $(p, q, r) \in R$ and atleast a triplet $(x, y, z) \in R$ such that

$$(p + q) \cdot r = p \cdot r + q \cdot r$$

$$(x + y) \cdot z \neq x \cdot z + y \cdot z$$

then the binary operation \cdot is said to be right Neutro distributive over $+$ on a set R .

A **right Nearring** is a set N together with two binary operations $+$ and \cdot such that:

- (1) $(N, +)$ is a group (not necessarily abelian)
- (2) (N, \cdot) is a semigroup
- (3) For all $n_1, n_2, n_3 \in N : (n_1 + n_2) \cdot n_3 = n_1 \cdot n_3 + n_2 \cdot n_3$ (right distribution law).

If $n_1 \cdot (n_2 + n_3) = n_1 \cdot n_2 + n_1 \cdot n_3$ instead of condition (3) then set N is a **left Nearring**.

NeutroNearing and their properties

A NeutroNearing is a Nearing that has either a Neutro-operation or a Neutro-axiom. In this paper we define NeutroNearing as below.

Definition 2.3. Let N be a nonempty set and let $+, \cdot : N \times N \rightarrow N$ be binary operations of ordinary addition and multiplication on N . The triple $(N, +, \cdot)$ is called a **left NeutroNearing** if the following conditions are satisfied:

- (i) $(N, +)$ is a NeutroGroup (not necessarily abelian)
- (ii) (N, \cdot) is a Neutro SemiGroup
- (iii) the left Neutro distributive law holds in N : that is there exists atleast one triplet $(a, b, c) \in N$ and atleast one triplet $(d, e, f) \in N$ such that:
 - $a \cdot (b + c) = a \cdot b + a \cdot c$
 - $d \cdot (e + f) \neq d \cdot e + d \cdot f$

Remark 2.4. If right Neutro distributive law holds in N : that is there exists atleast one triplet $(p, q, r) \in N$ and atleast one triplet $(s, t, u) \in N$ such that:

- $(p + q) \cdot r = p \cdot r + q \cdot r$
- $(s + t) \cdot u \neq s \cdot u + t \cdot u$

then N is called **right Neutro Nearing**.

Example 2.5. Let $X = \mathbb{Z}_{12}$ and let \oplus and \odot be two binary operations on X defined by $x \oplus y = x + 2y$ and $x \odot y = x + 4y$ for all $x, y \in X$ where “+” is addition modulo 12. Then (X, \oplus, \odot) is a NeutroNearing.

Example 2.6. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with “+” and “.” be binary operations defined on X as shown in the Cayley tables below:

+	a	b	c
a	c	c	b
b	c	b	c
c	c	c	b

·	a	b	c
a	b	a	a
b	a	c	a
c	a	a	b

It is clear from the table that :

$$(a + b) + c = a + (b + c) = b,$$

$$(c + a) + b = c, \text{ but } c + (a + b) = b \neq c$$

This shows that $(X, +)$ is a Neutro SemiGroup.

Next, let N_x and I_x represent additive neutral and additive inverse element respectively with respect to any element $x \in X$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} N_b &= b \\ I_b &= b \\ N_a &\text{ does not exist,} \\ I_b &\text{ does not exist.} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $(X, +)$ is a NeutroGroup.

Next, consider

$$\begin{aligned} b(cb) &= (bc)b \\ a(bc) &= b \text{ but } (ab)c = a \neq b \end{aligned}$$

This shows that (X, \cdot) is Neutro associative.

Lastly, consider

$$\begin{aligned} b.(b + b) &= b.b + b.b = c, \\ a.(b + c) &= a, \text{ but } a.b + a.c = c \neq a \end{aligned}$$

This shows that “ \cdot ” is left distributive over “ $+$ ”. Hence, $(X, +, \cdot)$ is a left NeutroNearing.

Note 2.7. Every NeutroRing is a NeutroNearing.

Notation: Let N be a NeutroNearing $d \in N$ is called Neutro distributive if there exist atleast two pairs (n_1, n_2) and $(m_1, m_2) \in N$ such that $(n_1 + n_2)d = n_1d + n_2d$ and $(m_1 + m_2)d \neq m_1d + m_2d$. Let $N_d = \{d \in N | d \text{ is Neutro distributive} \}$.

Remark 2.8. Let $(N, +, \cdot)$ be left NeutroNearing

- (i) If $(N, +)$ is Neutro abelian, then N is a Neutro abelian NeutroNearing.
- (ii) If (N, \cdot) is Neutro commutative then N is a Neutro commutative NeutroNearing.
- (iii) If $N = N_d$ then N is said to be Neutro distributive.
- (iv) If (N^*, \cdot) where $N^* = N \setminus 0$ is a Neutro group then N is called NeutroNearfield.

Theorem 2.9. Let $(N_i, +, \cdot), i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ be a family of NeutroNearrings. Then

- (1) $N = \cap_{i=1}^n N_i$ is a NeutroNearing.
- (2) $N = \prod_{i=1}^n N_i$ is a NeutroNearing.
- (1) *Proof.* Obvious \square

(2) *Proof.* Proof is by induction on n .

For $n = 1$ result is trivial. Let $n = 2$. Consider $N = N_1 \times N_2$ then is closed with respect to coordinate wise addition and coordinate wise multiplication. Note that there exist $n_1 \in N_1$ such that $n_1 + e_1 = n_1$ and there exist $n_2 \in N_2$ such that $n_2 + e_2 = n_2$.

Also, there doesnot exist additive identity for $n'_1 \in N_1$ and $n'_2 \in N_2$.

But $(n_1, n_2) \in N$ such that $(n_1, n_2) + (e_1, e_2) = (n_1, n_2)$ and there doesnot exist additive identity for $(n'_1, n'_2) \in N$.

Similarly one can observe the existence of Neutro additive inverse in N .

Since $(N_1, +)$ and $(N_2, +)$ are Neutro associative, there exist $a_1, b_1, c_1, a'_1, b'_1, c'_1 \in N_1$ and $a_2, b_2, c_2, a'_2, b'_2, c'_2 \in N_2$ such that $a_1 + (b_1 + c_1) = (a_1 + b_1) + c_1$

$$a_2 + (b_2 + c_2) = (a_2 + b_2) + c_2$$

$$a'_1 + (b'_1 + c'_1) \neq (a'_1 + b'_1) + c'_1$$

$$a'_2 + (b'_2 + c'_2) \neq (a'_2 + b'_2) + c'_2$$

Now, $(a_1, a_2), (b_1, b_2), (c_1, c_2), (a'_1, a'_2), (b'_1, b'_2), (c'_1, c'_2) \in N$ such that

$$(a_1, a_2) + [(b_1, b_2) + (c_1, c_2)] = (a_1, a_2) + [(b_1 + c_1, b_2 + c_2)] = (a_1 + (b_1 + c_1), a_2 + (b_2 + c_2))$$

$$= ((a_1 + b_1) + c_1, (a_2 + b_2) + c_2) = (a_1 + b_1, a_2 + b_2) + (c_1, c_2)$$

$$= [(a_1, a_2) + (b_1, b_2)] + (c_1, c_2)$$

$$\text{and } (a'_1, a'_2) + [(b'_1, b'_2) + (c'_1, c'_2)] \neq [(a'_1, a'_2) + (b'_1, b'_2)] + (c'_1, c'_2)$$

Similarly we prove (N, \cdot) is Neutro associative.

Further there exist $x_1, y_1, z_1, x'_1, y'_1, z'_1 \in N_1$ and $x_2, y_2, z_2, x'_2, y'_2, z'_2 \in N_2$ such that

$$x_1 \cdot (y_1 + z_1) = x_1 \cdot y_1 + x_1 \cdot z_1$$

$$x_2 \cdot (y_2 + z_2) = x_2 \cdot y_2 + x_2 \cdot z_2$$

$$x'_1 \cdot (y'_1 + z'_1) \neq x'_1 \cdot y'_1 + x'_1 \cdot z'_1$$

$$x'_2 \cdot (y'_2 + z'_2) \neq x'_2 \cdot y'_2 + x'_2 \cdot z'_2$$

But then, $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2), (z_1, z_2), (x'_1, x'_2), (y'_1, y'_2), (z'_1, z'_2) \in N$ such that

$$(x_1, x_2) \cdot [(y_1, y_2) + (z_1, z_2)] = (x_1, x_2) \cdot (y_1 + z_1, y_2 + z_2)$$

$$= (x_1(y_1 + z_1), x_2(y_2 + z_2)) = (x_1 \cdot y_1 + x_1 \cdot z_1, x_2 \cdot y_2 + x_2 \cdot z_2)$$

$$= (x_1 \cdot y_1, x_2 \cdot y_2) + (x_1 \cdot z_1, x_2 \cdot z_2) = (x_1, x_2) \cdot (y_1, y_2) + (x_1, x_2) \cdot (z_1, z_2)$$

$$\text{and } (x'_1, x'_2) \cdot [(y'_1, y'_2) + (z'_1, z'_2)] \neq (x'_1, x'_2) \cdot (y'_1, y'_2) + (x'_1, x'_2) \cdot (z'_1, z'_2)$$

$\therefore N$ is a NeutroNearing for $n = 2$.

Let $n > 2$. Assume the result for $n - 1$. Note that $M = \prod_{i=1}^{n-1} N_i$ forms a NeutroNearing with respect to coordinate wise addition and coordinate wise multiplication.

But then, $N = M \times N_n$ forms a NeutroNearing with respect to coordinate wise addition and coordinate wise multiplication. \square

Definition 2.10. Let $(N, +, \cdot)$ be a NeutroNearing. A nonempty subset S of N is called a **Neutro Near Subring** of N if $(S, +, \cdot)$ is also a NeutroNearing. The only trivial Neutro Near subring of N is N .

Theorem 2.11. Let $(N, +, \cdot)$ be a NeutroNearing and let $\{S_i\}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ be a family of Neutro Near Subrings of N . Then

- (1) $S = \bigcap_{i=1}^n S_i$ is a Neutro Near Subring of N .
- (2) $S = \prod_{i=1}^n S_i$ is a Neutro Near Subring of N .

Proof. Both result follows directly from Theorem 2.9. \square

Definition 2.12. Let $(N, +, \cdot)$ be a NeutroNearing. A nonempty subset I of N is called a **left Neutro Near ideal** of N if the following conditions hold:

- (1) I is a Neutro Near Subring of N .
- (2) There exist $x \in I$ such that $xr \in I, \forall r \in N$.

Definition 2.13. Let $(N, +, \cdot)$ be a NeutroNearing. A nonempty subset I of N is called a **right Neutro Near ideal** of N if the following conditions hold:

- (1) I is a Neutro Near Subring of N .
- (2) There exist $x \in I$ such that $rx \in I, \forall r \in N$

Definition 2.14. Let $(N, +, \cdot)$ be a NeutroNearing. A nonempty subset I of N is called a **Neutro Near ideal** of N if the following condition hold:

- (1) I is a Neutro Near Subring of N .
- (2) There exist $x \in I$ such that $xr, rx \in I, \forall r \in N$

Theorem 2.15. Let $(N, +, \cdot)$ be a NeutroNearing and let $\{I_i\}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ be a family of Neutro Near ideals of N . Then

- (1) $I = \bigcap_{i=1}^n I_i$ is a Neutro Near ideal of N .
- (2) $I = \sum_{i=1}^n I_i$ is Neutro Near ideal of N .

- (1) *Proof.* Since each $I_i, 1 \leq i \leq n$ is a Neutro Near Subring of N , it follows from Theorem 1.8 that $I = \bigcap_{i=1}^n I_i$ is a Neutro Near Subring of N .

Note that there exist $x_i \in I_i$ such that $x_i r, r x_i \in I_i, \forall r \in N$ and $\forall i, 1 \leq i \leq n$.

Let $y = x_1^2 x_2^2 \cdots x_n^2$. Then $y \in I_i, \forall i, 1 \leq i \leq n$.

For any $r \in N$ $ry, yr \in I_i, \forall i, 1 \leq i \leq n$

$\therefore y \in I$ with $ry, yr \in I$. \square

(2) Obivous.

Definition 2.16. Let $(N, +, \cdot)$ be a NeutroNearing and let I be a Neutro Near ideal of N . The set N/I is defined by

$$N/I = \{x + I : x \in N\}$$

For $x + I, y + I \in N/I$ with at least a pair $(x, y) \in N$, let \oplus and \odot be binary operations on N/I defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} (x + I) \oplus (y + I) &= (x + y) + I \\ (x + I) \odot (y + I) &= xy + I \end{aligned}$$

Then it can be shown that the tripple $(N/I, \oplus, \odot)$ is a NeutroNearing which we call Neutro-QuotientNearing.

Theorem 2.17. Let I be a Neutro Near ideal of the NeutroNearing $(N, +, \cdot)$. Suppose N is Neutro commutative NeutroNearing with Neutro unity then so is N/I .

Proof. There exist $a, b, c, d \in N$ such that $ab = ba$ and $cd \neq dc$.

But then $a + I, b + I, c + I, d + I \in N/I$ such that $(a + I)(b + I) = ab + I = ba + I = (b + I)(a + I)$ and $(c + I)(d + I) = cd + I \neq dc + I = (d + I)(c + I)$

Let e_y be a Neutro unity of N . Then there exist $y \in N$ such that $ye_y = e_yy = y$

But then $y + I \in N/I$ such that $(y + I)(e_y + I) = ye_y + I = y + I = (e_y + I)(y + I)$

$\therefore N/I$ is Neutro commutative NeutroNearing with Neutro unity $e_y + I$. \square

Definition 2.18. Let $(N, +, \cdot)$ and (S, \oplus, \odot) be any two NeutroNearings. The mapping $\phi : N \rightarrow S$ is called a NeutroNearing homomorphism if ϕ preserves the binary operations of N and S that is if for at least a pair $(x, y) \in N$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(x + y) &= \phi(x) \oplus \phi(y) \\ \phi(x \cdot y) &= \phi(x) \odot \phi(y) \end{aligned}$$

The kernel of ϕ denoted by $\ker\phi$ is defined as $\ker\phi = \{x \in N : \phi(x) = e_N\}$

Where $e_N \in N$ is a neutral element for at least one $n \in N$. The image of ϕ denoted by $Im\phi$ is defined as

$$Im\phi = \{y \in S : y = \phi(x)\}$$

for at least one $x \in N$. If in addition ϕ is a Neutro bijection, then ϕ is called a NeutroNearing isomorphism and we write $N \cong S$. NeutroNearing epimorphism, NeutroNearing monomorphism, NeutroNearing endomorphism and NeutroNearing automorphism are defined similarly.

Theorem 2.19. *Let R and S be two NeutroNearrings. Let $N_x = e_R$ for at least one $x \in R$ and let $N_y = e_S$ for at least one $y \in S$. Suppose that $\phi : R \rightarrow S$ is a Neutro Near homomorphism. Then:*

- (1) $\phi(e_R)$ is not necessarily equals e_S .
- (2) $Ker \phi$ is a Neutro Near Subring of R .
- (3) $Im \phi$ is not necessarily a Neutro Near Subring of S .
- (4) ϕ is Neutro injective if and only if $Ker \phi = \{e_R\}$ for at least one $e_R \in R$.

Theorem 2.20. *Let I be a Neutro Near ideal of a NeutroNearing $(N, +, \cdot)$. Then the mapping $\phi : N \rightarrow N/I$ defined by $\phi(x) = x + I$ is a NeutroNearing isomorphism with $Ker \phi = I$*

Proof. For atleast one pair x, y in N ,

$$\phi(x + y) = (x + y) + I = (x + I) + (y + I) = \phi(x) + \phi(y)$$

$$\text{and } \phi(xy) = xy + I = (x + I)(y + I) = \phi(x)\phi(y)$$

$$Ker \phi = \{x \in N | \phi(x) = e_{N/I}\}, \text{ where } e_{N/I} \in N/I \text{ such that } N_r = e_{N/I} \text{ for atleast one } r \in N/I$$

$$\cdot = \{x \in N | x + I = e_{N/I}\} = \{x \in N | x \in I\} = I \quad \square$$

Theorem 2.21. *Let $\phi : R \rightarrow S$ be a NeutroNearing homomorphism and let $K = Ker \phi$. Then the mapping $\psi : R/K \rightarrow Im \phi$ defined by $\psi(x + K) = \phi(x)$ is a NeutroNearing isomorphism.*

Proof. For atleast one pair $x, y \in R$

$$\psi((x + K) + (y + K)) = \psi((x + y) + K) = \phi(x + y) = \phi(x) + \phi(y)$$

$$= \psi(x + K) + \psi(y + K) \text{ and } \psi((x + K)(y + K)) = \psi((xy) + K) = \phi(xy) = \phi(x)\phi(y)$$

$$= \psi(x + K)\psi(y + K)$$

Also $Ker \psi = \{x + K \in R/K : \psi(x + K) = e_{Im \phi}\}$ where $e_{Im \phi} \in Im \phi$ such that $N_r = e_{Im \phi}$ for atleast $r \in Im \phi$.

$$= \{x + K \in R/K : \phi(x) = e_{Im \phi}\} = \{e_{R/K}\}$$

Thus ψ is a Neutro bijective Nearing homomorphism. \square

Note 2.22. *The above map ϕ is an epimorphism. So, we can treat ϕ as NeutroNearing epimorphism.*

Theorem 2.23. *NeutroNearing isomorphism of NeutroNearrings is an equivalence relation.*

Proof. Define a relation \sim as follows:

For any two NeutroNearrings N and N' , we say $N \sim N'$ iff there exist a Neutro Near ring isomorphism between N and N' . Clearly \sim is reflexive.

Suppose NeutroNearrings N, N' are such that $N \sim N'$, let $f : N \rightarrow N'$ be NeutroNearing isomorphism.

Then there exist $x, y \in N$ such that $f(x + y) = f(x) + f(y)$ and $f(xy) = f(x)f(y)$.

Now, $f(x), f(y) \in N'$ and

$$f^{-1}(f(x) + f(y)) = f^{-1}(f(x + y)) = x + y = f^{-1}(f(x)) + f^{-1}(f(y))$$

$$f^{-1}(f(x)f(y)) = f^{-1}(f(xy)) = xy = f^{-1}(f(x))f^{-1}(f(y))$$

$\therefore N' \sim N$ and f^{-1} is a NeutroNearing isomorphism.

Let $f : N \rightarrow N'$ and $g : N' \rightarrow N''$ be NeutroNearing isomorphisms.

Then $g \circ f : N \rightarrow N''$ is bijective and there exist $x', y' \in N'$ such that $g(x' + y') = g(x') + g(y')$ and $g(x'y') = g(x')g(y')$

Now, $x' = f(x), y' = f(y)$ for some $x, y \in N$ with $f(x + y) = f(x) + f(y)$ and $f(xy) = f(x)f(y)$

Consider,

$$\begin{aligned} g \circ f(x + y) &= g(f(x + y)) = g(f(x) + f(y)) = g(x' + y') = g(x') + g(y') = g(f(x)) + g(f(y)) \\ &= g \circ f(x) + g \circ f(y) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{and } g \circ f(xy) = g(f(xy)) = g(f(x)f(y)) = g(x'y') = g(x')g(y') = g(f(x))g(f(y))$$

$$= g \circ f(x)g \circ f(y)$$

$\therefore N \sim N'' \quad \square$

3. Conclusion

We have introduced in this paper the concept of NeutroNearrings by considering three NeutroAxioms(NeutroGroup(additive)), NeutroSemigroup(multiplicative) and left and right Neutro distributive laws(multiplication over addition). Several interesting results and examples on NeutroNearrings, NeutroSubrings, NeutroQuotientNearrings and NeutroNearing Homomorphisms are presented.

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